

Poor Clares, rich in music: unique polyphonic *Benedicamus Domino* settings from southern Polish convents in the late 13th and early 14th centuries

LATE medieval Clarist convents in Stary Sącz and Kraków in southern Poland became important repositories not only of plainchant but also of early polyphony. Manuscripts from the libraries of these cloisters contain several unique polyphonic pieces notated as additions in chant books or preserved as fragments. Five of these pieces are settings of the versicle *Benedicamus Domino*, in two- and three-part settings. They are likely the earliest witnesses to polyphony cultivated in these communities and offer a significant glimpse of local musical practices in medieval Poland. This article offers a new perspective on these compositions, through the identification of several concordances for the lower voices of the two-part *Benedicamus* settings, which show that the melodies used in some of these compositions travelled more widely than has previously been recognized. The new status of these lower voices as *cantus firmi* undermines the established assumption that these pieces were newly created by *Stimmtausch* (voice-exchange) principles, changing the broader polyphonic context in which they have typically been understood. In addition, a new concordance found in another Clarist source from Brussels containing two-part *Benedicamus* settings, reopens the discussion of the possible performance of polyphony by nuns in medieval Poland.

Clares and song

The Order of Poor Clares was founded by Clare of Assisi, whose Rule regulated the daily lives of the nuns with absolute austerity. Similarly harsh was her

attitude to liturgical chant. Clare's often-cited passage on the celebration of the Divine Office 'without singing' takes a definitely unfriendly position as regards music, with possible roots in her asceticism and her strict adherence to poverty.¹ Just as Clare's desire for abstinence was certainly mirrored in her denial of food, so too could it be witnessed in aspects of the liturgy.² Clare's ban on singing had also to do with gender division: the Franciscan brothers sang the Office, but the nuns were supposed only to recite it in speech, in order to deliver an even more pious rendition.³ Unlike Hildegard's sensuality and lavishness of language and music, Clare's bodily denial also excluded the voice. Several less stringent rules were, however, written for Poor Clare communities throughout the 13th century. Most of them, as in the case of the most liberal Rule of Urban IV (1263), allowed the holding of possessions and also permitted singing. Moreover, an abbess was given the power to foster the singing instruction of more literate and gifted nuns. The sisters in aristocratic foundations were called the 'rich Clares' and nuns in these cloisters were especially engaged in liturgical chant.

Spreading of the Order of St Clare in Poland: Salomea and Kinga

The Order of St Clare spread rapidly: by the 1230s there were almost 25 convents in Italy and many new foundations in other countries. The first community north of the Alps emerged as a result of the activities of Bohemian princess, St Agnes of Prague.

Her foundation of the convent in Prague in 1233 gave an impulse to start further Clarist communities in neighbouring Poland. The country, reigned by Bolesław V the Chaste (1226–79), High Duke of Poland, lived through a period of cultural prosperity with several newly founded monastic centres. The first Poor Clares cloister in Poland was founded in 1245 in Zawichost by Bolesław's sister, Blessed Salomea (1211/12–1268), and the second emerged in Wrocław in 1257. The third convent of the Order of St Clare in Stary Sącz was founded in 1280 by the duke's wife, the Grand Duchess of Poland, St Kinga of Hungary (c.1224–1292), followed by yet another foundation in Gniezno in 1283.

According to the 15th-century annals, the duke built his sister Salomea's nunnery in the town of Zawichost by Sandomierz at his own expense. He granted it 'twenty-five of the royal villages round about and in Sandomierz, as well as manors, lakes and tolls, sufficient for sixty women.'⁴ The large community was soon moved to Skała by Kraków shortly before 1260 while seeking protection from the Mongol and Lithuanian invasions.⁵ The sisters eventually moved within the city walls of Kraków and settled in St Andrew's church in 1320. Salomea's *vita* contains mostly descriptions of her numerous miracles.⁶ The Italian Franciscan preacher, Bartolomeo da Pisa, in his *Liber de conformitate*, written around 1390, mentions Salomea after the most prominent Clares nuns: Clara's sister Agnes, her mother Ortolana and St Agnes of Bohemia.⁷ This demonstrates Salomea's prestige and proximity to the women closest to the origins of the Clarist movement and to St Clare herself.

Bolesław's wife Kinga, founder of the convent of the Order of St Clare in Stary Sącz, became its abbess after her husband's death. Kinga's rich convent attracted women from patrician families and royalty. There were up to 30 Franciscan brothers who were responsible for the services and confessions, but the number of nuns approached 70.⁸ The convent in Stary Sącz became not only a kind of retirement place for high-born widows, but also served as a burial site for several female members of the Polish royal family. Also known as Cunegunda or Zinga, Kinga was the daughter of King Bela IV of Hungary and niece of St Elizabeth of Thüringen. She entered

marriage with Duke Bolesław with a vow to live in chastity. Called 'a woman of unusual piety', Kinga was involved in charitable works, helping the poor.⁹ As documented in the *Chronica XXIV Generalium Ordinis Fratrum Minorum*, of around 1370 and attributed to the Franciscan Arnaud de Sarrant, Kinga's holy way of life made her a serious contender for canonization.¹⁰ Despite the great respect from the Roman Curia, however, Kinga was only canonized centuries later in 1999. Five Poor Clare monasteries are still active in Poland today, but only those in Stary Sącz and Kraków can look back over a history of more than 700 years; the monastery in Stary Sącz has had a continued existence on the same site since its foundation.

Polish Rich Clares

The dowries that noble foundresses such as Salomea and Kinga brought to their monasteries made it possible for the nuns to own and use books. Both Salomea and Kinga were well educated and their foundations functioned as institutions of learning, where future queens and young women from noble houses were likely taught grammar, elementary theology, Latin and possibly music.¹¹ Following the example of Franciscan friars, Polish Clares strove for the prestigious title *moniales litteratae*. In this regard, it is significant that St Clare, mother of the Order, was portrayed in the early 14th-century noted psalter from Poor Clares cloister in Wrocław not with the typical image of a lamp, a monstrance or a lily, but rather carrying a book (see *illus.1*).¹²

Singing and instruction in singing, permitted by the Urbanist rule in all Polish Clare convents, required a minimum number of liturgical books for the performance of services. In Salomea's will, she bequeathed to the convent all the relics of saints, gold and silver chalices and exquisite decorations of the church. But the small private library that she had acquired—the books for 'chant' and 'study' ('libros autem tam chorales quam ad studium pertinentes')—was to be given to the friars.¹³

Kinga's *vita*, written by an anonymous Franciscan friar in the 14th century, provides not only a wealth of detail relating to her youth, married life and life in the monastery, but also some information about the importance of chant in Stary Sącz cloister. Kinga

1 St Clare carrying a book (PL-WRu I Q 233, fol.2r; reproduction permitted under Creative Commons CC BY-SA 3.0)

was admired for reciting (or perhaps singing) ten complete psalms apparently in the Polish vernacular ('in vulgari') with her nuns every day before leaving the church.¹⁴ The grand duchess was also known to have procured 'missals and other ecclesiastical books' ('missales vero ac alios ecclesiasticos libros').¹⁵ In Chapter XLV of her *vita* we read that she found much delight when the sisters devoutly sung Matins and their angelic voices would resonate in her ears ('et quanto melius et devocius sorores cantabant, tanto plus ex devocione ipsius voces angelice resonabant in auribus eius').¹⁶ Chapter XL—notably titled *De cantu*—describes an incident involving the Franciscan brothers with whom the nuns shared the church. Kinga wanted her sisters to advance in singing the Office; to encourage them to sing even more boldly ('et audaciam cantandi eis inferre'), she asked the brethren if the sisters could perform the Office chants on the feast of St Clare. The friars ignored her petition and started to sing

alone, much to the outrage of the nuns. Another time, as the nuns took over the sung Mass without permission and 'continued thunderingly' ('tonanter prosequerentur'), the brothers ostentatiously left the church but were forced to return by the mandate of the warden.¹⁷ These 'chant wars' show the power ascribed to singing and how persistent Kinga was in trying to enhance ecclesiastical worship in every fitting adornment ('ut ecclesiasticum cultum in omni decenti ornatu sublimaret'), be it a decorated robe or an adorned chant.¹⁸

Kinga's passion for music is reflected in the holdings of the Stary Sącz cloister library.¹⁹ Not only does it possess numerous 13th- and 14th-century graduals and antiphonaries, but it is also famous for its fragments of a so-called *Magnus liber* manuscript, containing almost 60 organa and motets of the Parisian Notre Dame school. The dating of the host manuscript from which these fragments came and the question of how it ended up in Poland

have been the subject of speculation for decades: Mirosław Perz suggested that the book originated in Poland in the 1280s, while Robert Curry proposed that it came from Paris at a relatively early period.²⁰ More recently, Katarzyna Grochowska has posited an English provenance for the fragments.²¹ Whatever their origin, the presence of fragments of a Parisian *Magnus liber*—whether sung or simply possessed—undoubtedly reflected a local interest in music, and indeed polyphonic music, which presumably also encouraged local musical performance and creativity. Manuscripts in both Sary Sącz and Kraków record several polyphonic genres, conductus, lectio and fragments of two-voice sequences, likely of Polish provenance. A particular interest in *Benedicamus Domino* settings is common to sources from both convents.

Benedicamus in Sary Sącz

The first short *Benedicamus* from the archive in Sary Sącz is found on one loose folio catalogued as in PL-SS Muz 7 and dated by Perz to around 1300.²² Even though it is monophonic, it is significant here in the context of its surrounding repertory. *Omnia beneficia*, a unique four-voice conductus with two strophes, is copied on the recto of the folio (see [illus.2](#)). On the verso we find the short Franciscan sequence *Ave mater gratie* with two double versicles (see [illus.3](#)), a sequence known from three other sources mostly belonging to the Central European Franciscan tradition but of which this Sary Sącz fragment is probably the earliest witness.²³

The *Benedicamus* chant is in the E mode—a rare occurrence, according to Michel Huglo, in whose provisional catalogue this melody does not

2 Four-voice conductus *Omnia beneficia* (PL-SS Muz 7, recto; reproduced with permission)

3 Sequence *Ave mater gratie* and *Benedicamus Domino* (PL-SS Muz 7, verso; reproduced with permission)

appear.²⁴ Barbara Barclay, unaware of the early Stary Sącz version, included this *Benedicamus* melody in her catalogue (as no.52), listing as its only source Codex Cuontz, a 16th-century sequentiary from St Gall (CH-SGs 546).²⁵ In Codex Cuontz the chant is found in many versions and for various liturgical occasions: troped as *Benedicamus flori nato* (fol.375v) and as *Benedicamus ad honorem dedicationis* (with the rubric ‘in dedicationibus Galli, Othmari etc.’, fol.375v) and untroped with the rubric ‘Benedicamus de b. Maria festum’ (fol.376v) (see ex.1).²⁶ Gallus and Othmar are early St Gall saints, but the use of this *Benedicamus* on Marian feasts could well apply to the version in the Stary Sącz fragment, where it is placed just after the sequence for the Virgin Mary. This Stary Sącz *Benedicamus* begins on *c*, instead of the *b*₄ in the versions in Codex Cuontz, and as a manuscript witness it is several centuries younger. It is intriguing that this monophonic *Benedicamus* is notated both underneath a sequence associated with the Franciscans, and also in close proximity to a unique four-voice conductus, one of only very few four-voice pieces known in the 13th century. The works in Muz 7 cannot definitively be declared local compositions, but this fragmentary witness nevertheless demonstrates that Stary Sącz had access to a rich and diverse musical repertory that is otherwise lost to posterity, and one that is notably absent from extant contemporary ‘central’ sources.

Sources from Stary Sącz also preserve polyphonic *Benedicamus* settings, two of which are notated as 14th-century additions in a Franciscan antiphoner that dates from the second half of the 13th century (PL-SS Muz 4, p.255, see illus.4).²⁷ This manuscript, if not actually copied at the convent, was certainly used there.²⁸ The first two-voice *Benedicamus* (hereafter *Benedicamus* I) shows a high degree of skilful management of its material, despite its relatively limited harmonic vocabulary (primarily 5ths and octaves). It consists essentially of five blocks (the sections with the words: *Benedicamus*, *Domino* and three distinctive *Alleluias*) with a final florid, organal-style ‘coda’ over a sustained tone. This piece has long been considered to belong to the broad family of *Stimmtausch* pieces, mostly note-against-note compositions based upon the strict principle of voice-exchange.²⁹ However, only

one phrase in the upper voice of *Benedicamus* I (on ‘Domino’) directly repeats the melody of the lower voice; the rest of the material is evidently newly composed in response to the pre-existing plainchant foundation.

Benedicamus I has its closest cognate in a slightly simpler polyphonic *Benedicamus* setting in Engelberg 314 (see ex.2).³⁰ Jacques Handschin suspected a *cantus firmus* melody at the root of this composition, but he was not sure which of the two parts it might be.³¹ Perz similarly suggested that some local Kyrie melody was the source of the lower voice of *Benedicamus* I Stary Sącz.³² In fact, both these pieces are based on a previously unidentified plainchant foundation, which appears in a 15th-century miscellany manuscript from St Gall (see ex.3).³³ The chant is copied there twice (on pp.76 and 77–8 respectively) within a collection of monophonic *Benedicamus* settings. The related polyphonic *Benedicamus* in both the Stary Sącz and Engelberg manuscripts are thus not true *Stimmtausch* compositions: they do not show the exact symmetry of phrases that is a condition of a strict voice-exchange principle, but rather take as their foundational voice a pre-existing *Benedicamus* plainchant melody.

Benedicamus II is written on the same staves as its precursor in Muz 4, and its lower voice is copied as a plainchant melody immediately above this polyphonic setting, within the main part of the antiphoner. In this case, then, the use of a plainchant foundation is unambiguous, with the chant melody copied in its own right nearby, under the rubric ‘laudes in dominica resurrectionis.’ The *Benedicamus* chant is in D mode, characterized by an opening ascending 5th, a semi-cadence on ‘alleluia’ on *a*, and a second melismatic ‘alleluia’ descending to the *finalis* and then rising to end on the 5th, *a*. This ending, in particular, is quite memorable, since *Benedicamus* melodies finishing on the 5th are scarce.

This *Benedicamus* plainchant melody was not included in Huglo’s catalogue, and Barclay labelled its origins ‘uncertain’, listing only its concordance in Codex Cuontz (fol.376r).³⁴ Perz suggested a genetic connection with a two-voice polyphonic elaboration of *Amborum sacrum*, the first trope of the third division of *Kyrie Cunctipotens genitor*, found

Ex.1 *Benedicamus Domino* in PL-SS Muz 7 and its cognates in CH-SGs 546

PL-SS Muz 77v
Be - ne - di - ca - mus Do - mi - no

CH-SGs 546, fol.376v
Be - ne - di - ca - mus Do - mi - no

CH-SGs 546, fol.375v
Be - ne - di - ca - mus flo - ri - na - to flo - ri pul - cher - ri - mo de - ra - di - ce stir - pis Yes - se Do - mi - no
De - o gra - ci - as

CH-SGs 546, fol.375v
Be - ne - di - ca - mus ad ho - no - rem de - di - ca - ti - o - nis hu - ius tem - pli con - se - cra - ti Do - mi - no

as a 14th-century addition in the Beromünster Cantatorium.³⁵ While the upper voice of composition in the Beromünster Cantatorium is different (especially at the beginning and towards the end), the original plainchant melody of the *Amborum* trope does indeed resemble the melodic shape of the lower plainchant voice of *Benedicamus* II in Sary Sącz. Although Perz did not pursue this connection any further, his observation is helpful. The *Amborum* trope melody was used as a *Benedicamus* melody and was notated in some 13th-century French manuscripts with *Benedicamus* collections using a cue naming the original source ('Amborum' or 'Amborum sacrum').³⁶ The *Amborum* trope melody is also found as a *Benedicamus* (but without a cue) in a notated missal from Exeter.³⁷ Apart from the already mentioned Cuontz version (with the rubric 'de sancte xii lectio ad laudes'), I have identified three further concordances of the plainchant (see ex.4). The earliest is notated in an English antiphoner from Worcester, dated c.1230. Like the Sary Sącz and Cuontz piece, this *Benedicamus* belongs to the Paschal formulary.³⁸ Another copy of this melody (without the *Alleluia*) appears again among Easter *Benedicamus* settings in a 15th-century St Gall *Liber ordinarius*.³⁹ And there is a notable further concordance (without any specification as to its liturgical function) in a 14th-century codex from the convent of St Clare in Brussels.⁴⁰

Both of the polyphonic *Benedicamus* compositions in Sary Sącz Muz 4 are clearly in a simple note-against-note style of counterpoint, moving between unison, 5th and octave sonorities. One could imagine that they represent traces of the kinds of more informal, oral traditions of making polyphony over a pre-existing plainchant melody that were never written down. This hypothesis is strengthened by the fact that the Sary Sącz and Engelberg versions of *Benedicamus* I are not identical, but rather only broadly similar: it seems that these are two independent written witnesses to essentially the same kind of polyphonic practice by which their common plainchant melody was elaborated. Charles Brewer believed both of the Sary Sącz *Benedicamus* settings 'may have been composed in Poland' or to be 'at least of Central European origin'.⁴¹ The survival of such polyphonic *Benedicamus* settings is a strong indication that there was a local tradition of *cantus planus binatim*.

Yet another polyphonic *Benedicamus* setting survives in Sary Sącz, although no musical or textual concordances can be identified in this instance. It is a fragmentary two-voice *Benedicamus* trope, ... *et via regens*, found on a loose folio (PL-SS Muz 8, see illus.5). Hesitation amongst scholars to acknowledge this piece as a *Benedicamus* trope is difficult to explain.⁴² Its text uses the typical lexis

255

gnus angelus autē domini descendit de celo alleluia **F**ubula **F**rat
autem aspectus eius sicut fulgur: uisumque eius sicut ignis alleluia al
leluia. **D**s dñs nris. **N**itmore autē eius ceterum sūt custodes et
facti sūt uelut monti alleluia. **B**enedicā. **R**espondēs autē an
gelus dixit mulieribz nolite timere facis enim quod thca q̄ntis alleluia
Laudate **H**ec dies quae fecit dominus
ceute mus et letet iure uite a
Et ualce mane una sabbato ueniunt ad monumentū ois iam
tole alleluia **B**enedicā. **B**enedicam⁹ dominus alleluia alle

4 Two polyphonic *Benedicamus* settings (PL-SS Muz 4, p.255; reproduced with permission)

Ex.2 *Benedicamus* I in PL-SS Muz 4 and the version in CH-EN 314

PL-SS Muz 4

Be - ne - di - ca - mus Do - mi - no, al - le - lu - ia,
al - le - lu - ia, al - le - lu - ia

CH-EN 314

Be - ne - di - ca - mus Do - mi - no, al - le - lu - ia,
al - le - lu - ia, al - le - lu - ia

of rhymed *Benedicamus* tropes, versus or conductus—such as *sine termino* and the final constellation with ‘ergo cetus noster letus / Benedicat Domino’—that leave little room for doubt as to the identity of the piece. Perz dated Muz 8 to c.1300, while Černý considered that it originated in the mid 14th century.⁴³ The folio is badly damaged but the text and the music are legible. The suggestion by Perz and Černý that the lower voice (‘vox principalis’) might have been borrowed from a chant cannot be correct.⁴⁴ The voices are clearly conceived together and neither presents a coherent melody that could exist on its own. In fact, the

piece is plainly a two-voice conductus. The setting is almost entirely in note-against-note style alternating melismatic and syllabic passages: the longest melismatic section comes, as is typical of conductus, at the end, on the word ‘Domino’. The voices move principally in parallel 5ths and octaves with minimal contrary motion, there is almost no voice-crossing, and the alignment of voices in melismatic sections is unproblematic.

Despite its missing beginning, a substantial portion of the piece survives. The second line of the extant text has a lone rhyme ‘-ium’ (*devium*) that must have characterized the lost preceding section.

Ex.3 Comparison of lower voice of *Benedicamus* I in PL-SS Muz 4, CH-EN 314 and CH-SGs 392

... et via	?a	... and on their way
regens devium.	5b	guiding the lost.
Stella previa	5a	Star going before us
per hec maria	5a	through these seas,
virgo regia	5a	royal virgin
plena gracia,	5a	full of grace,
Stella maris seculum	7c	star of the sea
lustrans cunctum populum	7c	illuminating the world:
ad perhennia	5a	to the eternal joys
transduc gaudia	5a	guide humanity,
ubi gloria	5a	where glory
manet sine termino.	7d	lasts without end.
Ergo cetus noster letus	4e + 4e	Thus, shall our joyful community
BENEDICAT DOMINO.	7d	praise the Lord.

Otherwise, the text is dominated by five-syllable lines with '-ia' endings, briefly interrupted by a pair of seven-syllable lines with the rhyme '-um'. In the concluding section the line 'manet sine termino' anticipates the syllable count and rhyme of the closing 'Benedicat Domino', which is directly preceded by a pair of shorter lines characterized by a new rhyme, '-us'. In its content, the text is a Marian *Benedicamus* trope, employing classic descriptions of and epithets for the Virgin as 'royal virgin full of grace', and 'guiding star of the sea' illuminating the way for lost mankind. Mary's name is not actually mentioned in the surviving text, but the context makes her the undeniable addressee, and the use of the plural of 'mare', 'maria' (the seas), is surely

intended as a pun.⁴⁵ In addition to more informal polyphonic elaborations of *Benedicamus* chants at Sary Sącz, therefore, the survival of this two-voice conductus is evidence that larger-scale and poetic elaborations of versicles were also considered of sufficient interest and/or practical use to find a place in the books of the convent.

Kraków *Benedicamus* settings

In addition to the survivals at Sary Sącz, various unique *Benedicamus* are also found among the archive of the Poor Clares cloister in Kraków. Two alternative polyphonic settings of the strophic *Benedicamus* trope *Surrexit Christus hodie* are transmitted in a 14th-century appendix to a late

Ex.4 Lower voice of *Benedicamus* II in PL-SS Muz 4 and its numerous concordances

PL-SS Muz 4, monophonic

 Be - ne - di - ca - mus Do - mi - no, al - le - lu - ia, al - le - lu - ia

PL-SS Muz 4, lower voice of the polyphonic version

 Be - ne - di - ca - mus Do - mi - no, al - le - lu - ia, al - le - lu - ia

Beromünster, Stiftskirche St. Michael, s. s., fol.60v, lower voice in the polyphonic version of the last trope

 Am - bo - rum sac - rum spi - ra - men nex - us a - mor - que e - ley - son

Paris, BN, lat. 17329, fol.248v, 'Amborum'

 Be - ne - di - ca - mus Do - mi - no

Paris, BN, lat. 1107, fol.396v, 'Amborum sacrum'

 Be - ne - di - ca - mus Do - mi - no

Manchester, John Rylands Library, lat. 24, fol.14v

 Be - ne - di - ca - mus Do - mi - no, al - le - lu - ia, al - le - lu - ia

CH-SGs 546, fol.376r

 Be - ne - di - ca - mus Do - mi - no, al - le - lu - ia, al - le - lu - ia

GB-WO 160, p.130 (fol.65r)

 Be - ne - di - ca - mus Do - mi - no, al - le - lu - ia, al - le - lu - ia

CH-SGs 448, p.43

 Be - ne - di - ca - mus Do - mi - no

CH-SGs 448, p.43 amended

 Be - ne - di - ca - mus Do - mi - no

Brussels, Koninklijke Bibliotheek van België/Bibliothèque Royale de Belgique, Ms.1870, fol.2r

 Be - ne - di - ca - mus Do - mi - no, al - le - lu - ia, al - le - lu - ia

13th-century gradual found in the library of St Andrew's convent.⁴⁶ Even though the gradual is considered to be the oldest Franciscan manuscript

on Polish soil, its earliest part was likely to be written before 1260 in a scriptorium outside Poland.⁴⁷ The manuscript was probably bought by the Blessed

5 A loose folio ... *et via regens* (PL-SS Muz 8; reproduced with permission)

Salomea and remained in use in Kraków long after her death.⁴⁸ It is impossible, however, to say how much Kraków nuns actually used the manuscript for their singing. As mentioned above, Salomea bequeathed her books to the Franciscan brothers rather than the Clarist sisters, and the rubric on fol.16r of the gradual reads ‘fratres’ (brothers).

The two settings of *Surrexit*—one in two voices, the other in three—are written on fol.155r (p.251, see [illus.6](#)). Their shared text, opening with the exclamation *Surrexit Christus hodie, Alleluia* and closing with the *Benedicamus* versicle followed by its response (*Deo gratias*), were clearly destined for performance during Paschal time. Both compositions belong to a network of related pieces in Bohemian sources: the connections are multiple, with varying degrees of musical and textual similarities.⁴⁹

The two-voice *Surrexit* (with parts named *superior* and *inferior* and written in unmeasured notation) is in the E mode and has three close cognates. The two-voice *Surrexit* transmitted in the

Jistebnický gradual shares the *superior* with the Kraków source, but its lower voice is completely different.⁵⁰ In another Prague manuscript, we find the melody concordant with the Kraków upper voice as a monophonic song with the text *In laudem sancti spiritus*. The same text appears in the Jistebnický gradual, without notation but with the rubric ‘cinitur sicut *Surrexit*’ (sung like *Surrexit*), thus confirming the connection.⁵¹ The third piece related to the two-voice Kraków *Surrexit* is an Ascension contrafactum *Ascendit Christus hodie*, found in a 16th-century manuscript in Chrudim.⁵² The Chrudim setting of *Ascendit* shares the melodies of both its *superior* and *inferior* voices with the Polish source.

The three-voice *Surrexit* in the Poor Clares gradual in Kraków labels its voices *superior*, *inferior* and *media*. In the *Alleluia* and *humano* sections, small *caudae* have been added to some *puncta*, and the entire piece therefore has the appearance of being in mensural notation, although the rhythmical interpretation remains highly problematic. Perz,

6 Two settings of the *Benedicamus* trope *Surrexit Christus hodie* (PL-Kklar Ms. 205, fol.155r; reproduced with permission)

taking into account the later date of the mensural additions, decided to transcribe the piece in equal values.⁵³ Paweł Gancarczyk offered a mensural interpretation, using the Italian systems of divisions.⁵⁴ In this case, only one concordance is known: a two-voice version (without the *media*) in a miscellany manuscript from the Cistercian cloister Vyšší Brod (Hohenfurt), dated 1410.⁵⁵ Černý considers this *Surrexit* a ‘Nachbildung’ of the above-mentioned two-voice *Ascendit* (that is, modelled on it) and offers a hypothetical two-voice archetype version of that piece.⁵⁶ He posits that the constant reworking of that model led to the creation of the three-voice setting in Kraków.⁵⁷ Based on the dating of the Kraków gradual, both *Surrexit* compositions in this Polish source seem to be the earliest settings with secure Central European origins.⁵⁸ It is striking that a scribe took the trouble to add both a two-voice and a three-voice setting of the same *Benedicamus* trope to an earlier manuscript. As at Stary Sącz, it

seems that the poetic and musical elaboration of the *Benedicamus Domino* versicle—perhaps especially at Eastertime—was central to the Clarist liturgy.

Conclusion

A particular interest in the provision of both monophony and polyphony for the *Benedicamus* in Poor Clare convents in Poland chimes with the evidence of later western European sources. In general, two- and three-part polyphony (sometimes even with vernacular text) is present in several 14th- and 15th-century manuscripts from Clarist cloisters in France, Switzerland and the Low Countries.⁵⁹ With regard to *Benedicamus* settings, as mentioned above, a 14th-century codex from a Clarist convent in Brussels contains musical notation only for its over 30 troped and untroped *Benedicamus* melodies and for its two polyphonic settings of the same chant. The first polyphonic setting has numerous concordances (including a version in Las Huelgas), while

the second is more limited in range and may reflect a modest local arrangement that would have been very suitable for most female voices. It seems that many different (most likely female) scribes added new *Benedicamus* melodies to this manuscript until the 16th century, the same kind of continued expansion of the repertory for the *Benedicamus* that also characterizes the sources in Sary Sącz and Kraków.

The broad dissemination of the newly presented concordances—in Swiss, French, Belgian and English sources—might be easier to connect with the travelling Franciscans than with strictly enclosed Clares. The mendicant friars moved across Europe and were likely mediators between different European centres and nunneries, such as the Franciscan female branch in Sary Sącz.⁶⁰ Yet even though there is an absence of concrete evidence attesting the presence of polyphonic singing in Clarist convents, it is Polish Rich Clares themselves that seem to have shown an interest in polyphony, and possibly also had the ability to perform it. Gancarczyk considers the performance of polyphony by Rich Clares ‘a fact’, hesitating only as to the degree to which imported manuscripts and repertories could have been integrated into the Clares’ musical practice.⁶¹ Similarly, Grochowska does not exclude the nun’s ability to perform Parisian motets found in fragments from the Sary Sącz cloister, noting that ‘the convent milieu offered

the ideal conditions for cultivating the newest and most exciting poetic and musical enterprises of the time’.⁶² In this context, at least the performance of local *cantus planus binatim* would seem only natural given the prestige, cultural *niveau* and economic possibilities provided by well-endowed communities founded by aristocratic patrons. Some powerful monasteries in Prague, Budapest or Königsfelden could ‘rival contemporary cathedrals and abbeys of monks’ in their splendour and the richness of their decoration.⁶³ In royal monasteries where members of the ruling family belonged to the churchgoers, ‘the celebration of the Divine Office and the Mass could turn into an impressive musical spectacle’.⁶⁴ The unusual predominance of simple-style *Benedicamus Domino* compositions in books from female cloisters, especially in the 1300s, is undisputed. Polish Clares might have been among the first to contribute to the aesthetic richness and development of their own liturgy, recording and maybe even creating new polyphonic *Benedicamus* settings—some with traces of improvisatory techniques, others more formally crafted—that serve the purpose well. Several examples of *Benedicamus* settings from the southern Polish convents show not only ‘the existence of a strong, durable tradition for Ars Antiqua-style polyphony in the kingdoms on Europe’s eastern borders’ but also deep and varied understanding of its forms and usage.⁶⁵

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Creativity for a Unique Moment in the Western Christian Liturgy c.1000–1500, led by Catherine A Bradley).

¹ Chapter 3: ‘1. Sorores litteratae faciant divinum officium secundum consuetudinem fratrum minorum 2. ex quo habere poterunt breviarum, legendo sine cantu’. See ‘Die Regel der Heiligen Klara’, in *Leben und Schriften der Heiligen Klara von Assisi*, ed. E. Grau and

M. Schlosser (Kevelaer, 2001), pp.227–93, at p.250.

² M. Natvig, ‘Rich Clares, poor Clares: celebrating the Divine Office’, *Women & Music*, iv (2000), p.61.

³ Natvig, ‘Rich Clares, poor Clares’, p.62.

⁴ *The annals of Jan Długosz*, trans. M. Michael (Chichester, 1997), pp.201–2.

⁵ J. Stoksik, ‘Powstanie i późniejszy rozwój uposażenia klasztoru Klarysek

w Krakowie w XIII i XIV wieku, *Rocznik Krakowski*, xxxv (1961), p.95.

⁶ 'Vita sanctae Salomeae Regine Haliciensis', in *Monumenta Poloniae Historica*, ed. A. Bielowski (Lviv, 1884), iv, pp.776–96.

⁷ *Analecta Franciscana*, iv (1906), p.358.

⁸ K. Kantak, *Franciszkanie Polscy, 1237–1517* (Kraków, 1937), p.27.

⁹ *The annals*, p.221.

¹⁰ *Analecta Franciscana*, iii (1897), p.222. In the 16th-century *Libro delle dignità*, Mariano da Firenze—a Franciscan who wrote the first history dedicated to the female Order—mentions the names of both Polish princesses in his hymn *Salve Christi sponsa Clara*, which enumerates the noble followers of St Clare. Salomea is also still mentioned among noble Clares in *Cum core e voce chiara*—a 15th-century *lauda* written by an anonymous Venetian nun. See *Cum hymnis et canticis*, ed. G. Boccali (Assisi, 2011), at pp.223–6 and p.281 respectively.

¹¹ K. Grochowska, 'Tenor circles and motet cycles: a study of the Stary Sącz manuscript [PL-SS Muz 9] and its implications for modes of repertory organization in 13th-century polyphonic collections' (PhD diss., University of Chicago, 2013), p.6.

¹² Wrocław, Biblioteka Uniwersytecka, I Q 233, fol.2r.

¹³ *Kodeks Dyplomatyczny Małopolski*, ed. F. Piekosiński (Kraków, 1876), p.92.

¹⁴ 'Vita et miracula Sanctae Kyngae Ducisse Cracoviensis', in *Monumenta Poloniae Historica*, ed. W. Kętrzyński (Lviv, 1884), iv, p.46 (*Item ex intencione proprie industrie consuetudo sibi in erat, quod decem psalmos in vulgari, antequam ecclesiam exiret, Deo persolvebat...*).

¹⁵ 'Vita et miracula', p.47.

¹⁶ 'Vita et miracula', p.59.

¹⁷ 'Vita et miracula', p.56.

¹⁸ 'Vita et miracula', p.46.

¹⁹ All the sources from Stary Sącz and Kraków have been described, reproduced and transcribed in *Sources of polyphony up to c.1500*,

ed. M. Perz, *Antiquitates Musicae in Polonia 13* (facsimiles) and *14* (transcriptions) (Warsaw and Graz, 1976).

²⁰ M. Perz, *The oldest sources of polyphonic music in Poland: fragments from Stary Sącz*, Polish Musicological Studies 1 (Kraków, 1977), pp.46–7; R. Curry, 'Fragments of Ars Antiqua music at Stary Sącz and the evolution of the Clarist order in Central Europe in the 13th century' (PhD diss., Monash University, 2003), p.241.

²¹ Grochowska, 'Tenor circles', pp.419–44.

²² In this article, to avoid the problem of incomplete and outdated call numbers of Stary Sącz holdings, I use the system of sigla by Grochowska ('Tenor circles', pp.20–1), which encompasses the content of both monophonic and polyphonic items. On the dating of Muz 7, see *Sources*, iv, p.xx.

²³ The other sources of this piece are: a 14th-century Franciscan or Clarist gradual (Prague, Národní knihovna, Ms. I E 12, fols.77v–78r); a 15th-century codex with chant and polyphony connected to the Franciscans kept in Wrocław (Biblioteka Uniwersytecka, I Q 466, fols.12v–13v); and a 14th-century English missal (London, British Library, Add. Ms. 11414, fol.300r) with only the extended text of this sequence.

²⁴ M. Huglo, 'Les débuts de la polyphonie à Paris: les premiers "organa" parisiens', *Forum musicologicum*, iii (1982), p.119.

²⁵ B. Barclay, 'The medieval repertory of polyphonic untroped *Benedicamus Domino* Settings' (PhD diss., University of California, 1977), i, p.71.

²⁶ These troped versions were not listed by Barclay. The same melody is also used for numerous instances of the *Ite missa est* on fol.377v.

²⁷ *Sources*, xiv, p.xxxij. J. Černý believes that the *terminus post quem* should be c.1350 ('Czeski aspekt polskich źródeł polifonii średniowiecznej', *Muzyka*, xxi (1976), p.86). C. Brewer considers

the polyphonic additions as being copied earlier than 14th century ('The introduction of the *Ars Nova* into East Central Europe: a study of late medieval Polish sources' (PhD diss., City University of New York, 1984), p.122).

²⁸ Brewer, 'The introduction', p.118.

²⁹ Barclay, 'The medieval repertory', i, pp.557 and 612–17; Černý, 'Czeski aspekt', pp.87–8; Brewer, 'The introduction', pp.117–19; M. Perz, 'O dwugłosowych *Benedicamus Domino* klarysek w Starym Sączu', *Przegląd Muzykologiczny*, v (2005), pp.9–10; M. S. Cuthbert, 'Trecento fragments and polyphony beyond the codex' (PhD diss., Harvard University, 2006), esp. pp.332–3 and 394–9.

³⁰ Engelberg, *Stiftsbibliothek*, cod. 314, fol.127r. Handschin's transcription contains several mistakes and he seems to be unaware of the Polish source (J. Handschin, 'Angelomontana polyphonica', *Schweizer Jahrbuch für Musikwissenschaft*, iii (1928), pp.4–5). Despite the absence of rhythmic information in the manuscript's notation, Barclay employs modal rhythm in her transcription ('The medieval repertory', ii, p.211).

³¹ Handschin, 'Angelomontana', p.73.

³² Perz, 'O dwugłosowych *Benedicamus Domino*', p.9.

³³ St Gall, *Stiftsbibliothek*, Ms. 392.

³⁴ Barclay listed it under item 107 ('The medieval repertory', i, p.91) but she misread the mode of the piece, transcribing it in G (i, pp.91, 499), although her transcription of the piece itself is correct in *d* (ii, p.219). This false reading led Barclay to a further incorrect assumption that this melody is employed as the tenor of a *Benedicamus organum duplum* setting in the Notre Dame repertory (i, p.617).

³⁵ Perz, 'O dwugłosowych *Benedicamus Domino*', p.11. Beromünster, *Stiftskirche St Michael*, s. s. (*olim* II. c. 2.). Transcription in A. Geering, *Die Organa und mehrstimmigen Conductus in den Handschriften des deutschen Sprachgebietes vom 13. bis 15. Jahrhundert* (Bern, 1952), p.85.

- ³⁶ A. W. Robertson, “Benedicamus Domino”: the unwritten tradition, *Journal of the American Musicological Society*, xli (1988), esp. pp.12–32. The *Benedicamus* in question appears in two manuscripts in held in Paris, Bibliothèque Nationale de France: lat. 1107 (fol.396v) and lat. 17329 (fol.248v).
- ³⁷ Manchester, John Rylands Library, lat. 24, fol.14v.
- ³⁸ Worcester, Cathedral Library, Ms. 160 (*olim* 1247), p.130. This is item 28 in Barclay’s catalogue, but the similarity of the melodic shape with the Stary Sącz and Codex Cuontz versions escaped her attention (“The medieval repertory”, i, p.62).
- ³⁹ St Gall, Stiftsbibliothek, Cod. 448. The scribe’s mistake—beginning with the leap of a 4th instead of a 5th—is easily emended.
- ⁴⁰ Brussels, Koninklijke Bibliotheek van België/Bibliothèque Royale de Belgique, Ms. 1870, fol.2r.
- ⁴¹ Brewer, ‘The introduction’, p.123.
- ⁴² Brewer, ‘The introduction’, p.124; *Sources of polyphony*, xiv, p.166; Perz, ‘Quattro esempi sconosciuti del cantus planus binatim in Polonia’, in *Memorie e contributi alla musica dal medioevo all’età moderna offerti a F. Ghisi nel settantesimo compleanno (1901–1971)* (Bologna, 1971), i, p.98.
- ⁴³ *Sources*, xiv, p.166; Černý, ‘Česki aspekt’, p.86.
- ⁴⁴ Perz, ‘Quattro esempi’, p.98; Černý, ‘Česki aspekt’, p.86.
- ⁴⁵ Perz missed this common word-play and mistakenly read here the name ‘Maria’; see *Sources*, xiv, p.166; ‘Quattro esempi’, pp.98–9.
- ⁴⁶ Kraków, Biblioteka Klasztoru św. Andrzeja, Ms. 205.
- ⁴⁷ F. Bąk, ‘Średniowieczne graduały franciszkańskie’, *Musica Medii Aevi*, iii (1969), p.92; M. Szczotka, ‘Trzynastowieczny graduał ms. 205 z Biblioteki Klarysek Krakowskich w świetle polskiej i europejskiej tradycji liturgiczno-muzycznej: Studium źródłoznawcze’, *Archiwa, Biblioteki i Muzea Kościelne*, lxxi (1999), pp.294 and 356–7.
- ⁴⁸ Szczotka, ‘Trzynastowieczny graduał ms. 205’, pp.256 and 358.
- ⁴⁹ Černý, ‘Středověký vícehlas v českých zemích’, *Miscellanea musicological*, xxvii/xxviii (1975), pp.59–70; Brewer, ‘The introduction’, pp.139–42.
- ⁵⁰ Prague, Knihovna Národního muzea, Ms. xii f 14, fol.199r–v. Brewer mistakenly describes *Surrexit* in this source as monophonic, whereas it is clearly a two-part setting. ‘The introduction’, p.139.
- ⁵¹ Prague, Národní knihovna, Ms. v.H.11, fol.24r–v. This melody is written out twice—with the text of the first strophe and then with five-fold *Alleluia*. Three further strophes with an implied interpolation of the *Alleluia* strophe follow. In *laudem* is followed in the Prague manuscript by a monophonic *Pangamus melos glorie* (fol.24v) with a very similar melody and by the monophonic *Surrexit Christus hodie* (fol.24v) with seven strophes. The beginning of this piece is similar to the lower voice of the Kraków *Surrexit* but afterwards it does not resemble it at all.
- ⁵² Chrudim, Regionální muzeum, Ms. 12580, fol.281r. On fol.281r–v there are three different polyphonic settings of *Ascendit*: two mensural ones in F and in D modes and the third version in E mode, written in unmeasured notation. This last one perfectly matches the *Surrexit* version in Kraków. Brewer’s assumption (“The introduction”, p.139) that the monophonic setting of *Ascendit* in Moosburg is ‘similar to the upper voice of the Kklar 205 [*Surrexit*] version’ is not correct.
- ⁵³ *Sources*, xiv, p.482.
- ⁵⁴ P. Gancarczyk, ‘Musica mensuralis w polskich źródłach muzycznych do 1600 roku’, in *Notae musicae artis. Notacja muzyczna w źródłach polskich XI–XVI wieku*, ed. E. Witkowska-Zaremba (Kraków, 1999), p.395.
- ⁵⁵ Vyšší Brod, Klášterní knihovna, Ms. 42, fol.151v.
- ⁵⁶ Černý, ‘Středověký vícehlas’, p.115.
- ⁵⁷ Černý, ‘Středověký vícehlas’, p.115.
- ⁵⁸ Brewer, ‘The introduction’, p.142.
- ⁵⁹ Natvig, ‘Rich Clares, poor Clares’, p.70. Natvig seems unaware of the polyphonic pieces in Stary Sącz and Kraków.
- ⁶⁰ Grochowska, ‘Tenor circles’, pp.444–7.
- ⁶¹ Gancarczyk, ‘Polyphonic music in fragments: a new perspective for Polish musicology?’, *Musicology Today*, x (2013), p.16.
- ⁶² Grochowska, ‘Tenor circles’, p.456.
- ⁶³ C. Jäggi and U. Lobbedey, ‘Church and cloister: the architecture of female monasticism in the Middle Ages’, in *Crown and veil: female monasticism from the fifth to the fifteenth centuries*, ed. J. F. Hamburger and S. Marti (New York, 2008), p.126.
- ⁶⁴ B. Roest, *Order and disorder: the Poor Clares between foundation and reform*, The Medieval Franciscans 8 (Brill, 2013), pp.253–4.
- ⁶⁵ Brewer, ‘The introduction’, p.106.

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Poor Clares, rich in music: unique polyphonic *Benedicamus Domino* settings from southern Polish convents in the late 13th and early 14th centuries

Under the reign of Duke Bolesław V, Poland lived through a period of cultural prosperity with several newly founded monastic centres and productive scriptoria. Particularly important were two convents of the Order of St Clare, founded by the duke's sister, the blessed Salomea, and his wife, St Kinga. Both cloisters were led in the spirit of royal foundations and were important repositories of medieval chant and polyphony. While Stry Sącz (founded 1280) is famous for preserving several polyphonic

unica, such as the four-part conductus *Omnia beneficia* and fragments of Notre Dame motets, it also contains contrary-motion two-voice *Benedicamus* settings, added beneath monophonic *Benedicamus* melodies, which seem to be written records of the kinds of oral polyphonic practices common in female cloisters. Unique two- and three-part troped *Benedicamus* settings are also preserved in the archive in Kraków, where they too were a late addition to an earlier manuscript, revealing a particular interest in the provision of notated polyphony for the *Benedicamus*. This article investigates these polyphonic *Benedicamus* settings in their broader liturgical context. It identifies several new plainchant concordances and reflects on the status of music and polyphony in the Clarist Order in southern Poland.

Keywords: *Benedicamus Domino*; Stry Sącz; Polish Clares; Kraków; early polyphony; Clarist nuns